

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИЧИНЫ ЗАИМСТВОВАНИЯ СЛОВ ИЗ ДРУГИХ ЯЗЫКОВ

LINGUISTIC AND PSYCHOLOGICAL REASONS TO BORROW WORDS FROM OTHER LANGUAGES

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В данной статье анализируются современные лексические заимствования слов и предлагается углубленное изучение лингвистических и психологических мотиваций данного явления. На основе отобранных примеров из российских медиа ресурсов в исследовании рассматриваются заимствованные слова. Приводится классификация этой лексики по языковым особенностям, подкрепленная примерами. Результаты анализа указывают на происхождение заимствованных слов из множества языков. Причины заимствования слов, выявленные в ходе исследования, охватывают множество факторов. В работе подчеркивается важность заимствованных слов для обогащения словарного запаса и культурного разнообразия языка.

This article analyzes modern lexical borrowings of words and offers an in-depth study of the linguistic and psychological motivations of this phenomenon. Based on selected examples from Russian media resources, the study examines borrowed words. The classification of this vocabulary by language features is given, supported by examples. The results of the analysis indicate the origin of loanwords from a variety of languages. The reasons for borrowing words identified in the course of the study cover many factors. The paper emphasizes the importance of borrowed words for enriching the vocabulary and cultural diversity of the language.

Ключевые слова: *заимствованные слова, заимствованные термины, причины заимствования, языковое взаимодействие, обогащение языка.*

Key words: *borrowed words, borrowed terms, reasons of borrowing, linguistic interaction, language enrichment.*

Introduction.

The rate of enrichment of the vocabulary of the language with borrowed words is accelerating today due to the progress of modern technologies. The roll call of languages through historical epochs, starting from the time of incipient contacts between ancient peoples, in wars and in the process of developing new territories, opened the way for constant and non-stop borrowing. As part of the study of the languages of the world, we find that the exchange of lexical and grammatical material occurs everywhere. It is noted that the process of integrating borrowed words may occur unconsciously, especially among the younger generation – children and adolescents. Teenagers incorporate foreign words into their speech, often without even realizing that they are taken from foreign languages, mistakenly considering them native. The main motives for borrowing vocabulary units in modern times are the subject of our scientific consideration.

The language systems of each nation demonstrate considerable flexibility and openness, which is manifested in the introduction of borrowed words. Russian, like many others, is no exception – everyday communication is saturated with an extensive arsenal of borrowings. These words, having migrated from various languages, not only enrich the lexical composition, but also have a significant impact on the cultural dynamics of society. The emergence of new vocabulary, in turn, affects numerous aspects of life, affecting the cultural and social structure. The reasons for the introduction of new vocabulary into the language are diverse and multilevel phenomena of interlinguistic interaction

Research Material.

Studying modern Russian fiction, there is a significant penetration of loanwords and neologisms. This phenomenon, which covers a wide range of social spheres, from computer technology to sports names, is reflected in both economic and financial terms, says L.P. Krysin, an outstanding linguist, expert in the fields of lexicology, semantics, stylistics, lexicography and sociolinguistics. The flourishing of foreign tourism, strengthening of ties in business, scientific, commercial and cultural fields contributed to the increased contacts with native speakers of foreign languages, which, in turn, led to the enrichment of the linguistic palette of Russian society.

In the light of these processes, an important aspect is to analyze the reasons for the inclusion of borrowed terms in the artistic heritage, as well as to assess the degree of their use. These aspects are of great interest to linguists and philologists, as they reflect linguistic transformations that relate to the cultural essence of the people. The disintegration of the Soviet Union, according to Krysin, became one of the fundamental factors that led to these linguistic changes. In the course of the study, the reasons for the use of borrowed words in modern Russian literature were considered, noting their significant impact on not only these areas, but also other elements of social life, including art [7, p. 1].

Thus, the art of words in the Russian literary canon takes on new forms under the influence of borrowed expressions, which means that language is a living organism demonstrating the adaptation and absorption of cultural and social realities of the time. This research was engaged in studying and borrowing terminology from foreign sources, based on articles from the electronic version of Komsomolskaya Pravda. During the analysis of the material consisting of borrowed words, their systematization was carried out by categories: parts of speech, languages of their origin and the presence of Russian analogues. The study sought to find out the reasons for the use of these lexical borrowings in modern Russian-language media. For the selection of borrowed words, the method of continuous sample analysis was used, based on the materials of the newspaper "Komsomolskaya Pravda".

Analysis of reasons to borrow new words.

As part of the initial stage of the research work, the selection of borrowed words used by the authors of publications in the mentioned newspaper from various languages was carried out using the continuous sampling method. The number of such lexical borrowings is determined to be 32.

These borrowings are represented by nouns (15 words, for example, термометр, идеология, платформа, онлайн, реалити-шоу, тревел-шоу, министр, президент, параметр, анализ, кандидат, фракция, оппозиция, финансирование, эксперт и т. д.), adjectives (8 words, for example, документальный, кабельный, минимальный, политический, парламентский, автоматический, уникальный, официальный и т. д.), verbs (4 words, for example, арестовали, финишировала, реагировать, отклонять и), short adjective (for example, стабилен) and adverb (2 words, for example, абсолютно, фактически) [5]. At the second stage, the borrowed words were classified by language and the presence of an analogue in Russian.

To select borrowed words, we turned to:

The Etymological online dictionary of the Russian language by G.A. Krylov [2]. The etymological online dictionary of the Russian language by N.M. Shansky [4]. The etymological online

dictionary of the Russian language by A.V. Semenov [6]. The etymological online dictionary of the Russian language by Max Fasmer [3].

On the basis of the above dictionaries, the borrowed words were divided into etymological groups: Latin (13 lexical units, for example, президент, кандидат, оппозиция, эксперт, документальный, кабельный, минимальный, парламентский, официальный, реагировать, стабилен, абсолютно, фактически и т. д.), French (3 lexical units, for example, платформа, министр, фракция, и т. д.), German (1 lexical unit, for example, арестовали, и т. д.), Greek (7 lexical units, for example, термометр, идеология, параметр, анализ, политический, автоматический, наклонять и т. д.), English (5 lexical units, for example, онлайн, реалити-шоу, тревел, финансирование, финишировала, и т.д.), Proto-Indo-European (1 lexical unit, например уникальный, и т. д.). There were also words that had an equivalent in Russian (34 lexical units, for example, президент (вождь), оппозиция (борьба), эксперт (умелец), документальный (достоверный), минимальный (простейший), реагировать (откликаться), стабилен (устойчив), абсолютно (совершенно), фактически (очевидно), платформа (помост), фракция (союз), арестовали (задержали), идеология (миросозерцание), анализ (обзор), уникальный (единственный), and words that have no equivalent (14 lexical units, for example, кандидат, кабельный, парламентский, официальный, министр, термометр, параметр, политический, автоматический, онлайн, реалити-шоу, тревел, финансирование, финишировать и т. д.). Having analyzed the use of borrowed words in the modern Russian media space, we have identified several motives for the integration of foreign languages in this area. One of the first is the interaction of Russia with Byzantium in the XII century, which caused the appearance of words like "expert" and "thermometer", introduced from Latin and Greek. Such cooperation with that state facilitated the penetration of foreign language terms. Military clashes on the territory of Russia and abroad have also played a significant role. Russians Russian-French War (1812-1814), for example, contributed to the spread of French words like "platform" in the Russian language.

In addition, in the XVIII century, French proved to be the language of the aristocracy and nobility, introducing such borrowings as "minister" and "faction". The technological development of the 20th century gave rise to a fourth layer of borrowings, represented mainly by the names of innovations and various devices taken from English and German, such as "arrest" and "finish". The multifaceted influence of foreign languages demonstrates the importance of their influence on the development of the Russian lexical corpus. – In their research, scientists such as L.P. Krysin and E. Richter identified the key motivating factors contributing to the emergence of novelty in language, necessitating the naming of new phenomena and concepts. The progress of technological innovations, the emergence of devices and other innovations in the market contributes to the introduction and adaptation of borrowed terms. In particular, terms like "online" and others originated and took root in the Russian-speaking environment precisely as a result of such processes at the dawn of the XXI century. Words of foreign origin have gained popularity and have become elements of loans not only because of their functional value, but also because of their inherent prestige or euphony. People who actively use such terms in their speech often stand out from others, creating the impression of themselves as educated, informed, and thus promote the spread of borrowed words. The tendency to strive for compression and compactness in naming objects and phenomena in one word is also significant, which also encourages borrowing from foreign languages; The motivation is the lack of exact analogues in the Russian vocabulary. The combination of the above factors produces a huge number of borrowed words in the modern media sphere of Russia.

Conclusion.

During the study of the materials of the newspaper Komsomolskaya Pravda, it was found that the Russian language is actively replenished with borrowings. Analyzing the reasons for the popularization of borrowed words, it is possible to identify events that had a significant impact on this process: diplomatic relations between Russia and Byzantium in the XII century, military conflicts,

fascination with the French language in the upper strata of society of the XVIII century and scientific and technological progress of the XX century. The language is enriched with new verbal expressions that affect many aspects of society, including the media.

Throughout this research, words of foreign origin have been identified and systematized, the dominant sources of which are Latin, French, Greek and English, as well as a group of words taken from several foreign languages at the same time. These borrowed lexical units permeate all spheres of our lives, becoming integral in people's speech. The data obtained and their further analysis will serve as the basis for an in-depth study of the causes of the appearance and spread of borrowed words in the Russian language.

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